

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 33

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 33

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 33:1 Sing for joy in the LORD, O you righteous ones; Praise is becoming to the upright. ² Give thanks to the LORD with the lyre; Sing praises to Him with a harp of ten strings. ³ Sing to Him a new song; Play skillfully with a shout of joy. ⁴ For the word of the LORD is upright, And all His work is done in faithfulness. ⁵ He loves righteousness and justice; The earth is full of the lovingkindness of the LORD.</p>	<p>Psa. 33:1 לִישָׁרִים נֶאֱמָה תְהִלָּה: ² הוֹדוּ לַיהוָה בְּכִנּוֹר בְּנֶבֶל עֲשׂוּר וּמְרוּ-לוֹ: ³ שִׁירֵי-לוֹ שִׁיר תְּרַשׁ הִיטִיבוּ נֶגֶן בַּתְרוּעָה: ⁴ כִּי-יִשָּׂר דְּבַר-יְהוָה וְכָל-מַעֲשָׂהּ בְּאֱמוּנָה: ⁵ אֱהָב צְדָקָה וּמִשְׁפָּט תִּסְדֵּר יְהוָה מִלְּאֵה הָאָרֶץ: ⁶ בְּדַבַּר יְהוָה שָׁמַיִם נִעֲשׂוּ וּבְרוּחַ בָּיִת כָּל-צְבָאָם: ⁷ כִּנֹּס כִּנּוֹד מִיַּיָּם נִתְּן בְּאֲצָרוֹת תְּהוֹמוֹת: ⁸ יִירָאוּ מִיְהוָה כָּל-הָאָרֶץ מִמַּנּוֹ יִגְזְרוּ כָּל-יֹשְׁבֵי תֵבֶל: ⁹ כִּי הוּא אָמַר וַיְהִי הוּא-צִוָּה וַיַּעֲמֵד: ¹⁰ יְהוָה הִפִּיר עֲצַת-גּוֹיִם הִנְיָא מִחֲשָׁבוֹת עַמִּים: ¹¹ עֲצַת יְהוָה לְעוֹלָם תִּעֲמָד מִחֲשָׁבוֹת לְבוֹ לְדָר וָדָר: ¹² אֲשֶׁרֵי תִגּוֹי אֲשֶׁר-יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵיוּ הָעַם אֶבְתָּר לְנִתְלָה לֹא: ¹³ מִשָּׁמַיִם תִּבְיֵט יְהוָה רְאָה אֶת-כָּל-בְּנֵי הָאָדָם: ¹⁴ מִמְּכוֹר-</p>
<p>Psa. 33:6 By the word of the LORD the heavens were made, And by the breath of His mouth all their host. ⁷ He gathers the waters of the sea together as a heap; He lays up the deeps in storehouses. ⁸ Let all the Earth fear the LORD; Let all the inhabitants of the world stand in awe of Him. ⁹ For He spoke, and it was done; He commanded, and it stood fast. ¹⁰ The LORD nullifies the counsel of the nations; He frustrates the plans of the peoples.</p>	<p>תִּסְדֵּר יְהוָה מִלְּאֵה הָאָרֶץ: ⁶ בְּדַבַּר יְהוָה שָׁמַיִם נִעֲשׂוּ וּבְרוּחַ בָּיִת כָּל-צְבָאָם: ⁷ כִּנֹּס כִּנּוֹד מִיַּיָּם נִתְּן בְּאֲצָרוֹת תְּהוֹמוֹת: ⁸ יִירָאוּ מִיְהוָה כָּל-הָאָרֶץ מִמַּנּוֹ יִגְזְרוּ כָּל-יֹשְׁבֵי תֵבֶל: ⁹ כִּי הוּא אָמַר וַיְהִי הוּא-צִוָּה וַיַּעֲמֵד: ¹⁰ יְהוָה הִפִּיר עֲצַת-גּוֹיִם הִנְיָא מִחֲשָׁבוֹת עַמִּים: ¹¹ עֲצַת יְהוָה לְעוֹלָם תִּעֲמָד מִחֲשָׁבוֹת לְבוֹ לְדָר וָדָר: ¹² אֲשֶׁרֵי תִגּוֹי אֲשֶׁר-יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵיוּ הָעַם אֶבְתָּר לְנִתְלָה לֹא: ¹³ מִשָּׁמַיִם תִּבְיֵט יְהוָה רְאָה אֶת-כָּל-בְּנֵי הָאָדָם: ¹⁴ מִמְּכוֹר-</p>

¹¹ The counsel of the LORD stands forever,

The plans of His heart from generation to generation.

¹² Blessed is the nation whose God is the LORD,

The people whom He has chosen for His own inheritance.

Psa. 33:13 The LORD looks from heaven;

He sees all the sons of men;

¹⁴ From His dwelling place He looks out

On all the inhabitants of the Earth,

¹⁵ He who fashions the hearts of them all,

He who understands all their works.

¹⁶ The king is not saved by a mighty army;

A warrior is not delivered by great strength.

¹⁷ A horse is a false hope for victory;

Nor does it deliver anyone by its great strength.

Psa. 33:18 Behold, the eye of the LORD is on those who fear Him,

On those who hope for His lovingkindness,

¹⁹ To deliver their soul from death
And to keep them alive in famine.

²⁰ Our soul waits for the LORD;
He is our help and our shield.

²¹ For our heart rejoices in Him,
Because we trust in His holy name.

²² Let Your lovingkindness, O LORD, be upon us,

According as we have hoped in You.

שְׁבֹתוֹ הַשְּׁמִימָה אֵל כָּל־יֹשְׁבֵי

הָאָרֶץ : ¹⁵ הַיֵּצֵר יַחַד לְבָבָם

¹⁶ הַמְּבִין אֶל־כָּל־מַעֲשֵׂיהֶם :

אֵין־הַמְּלֶךְ נוֹשֵׁעַ בְּרַב־חַיִּל

¹⁷ וְגִבּוֹר לֹא־יִנָּצֵל בְּרַב־כֹּחַ :

וְשֹׁקֵר הַסּוֹס לְתַשׁוּעָה וּבְרַב

חַיִּלוֹ לֹא יִמְלֹט : ¹⁸ הַנֶּהָ עֵינַי

יְהוָה אֶל־יְרֵאָיו לְמִי־חַלִּים

לְחַסְדָּו : ¹⁹ לְהַצִּיל מִמָּוֶת נַפְשָׁם

וּלְחַיּוֹתָם בְּרָעַב : ²⁰ נַפְשֵׁנוּ

חִבָּתָה לִיתְהוָה עֲזָרְנוּ וּמִגִּבּוֹרֵנוּ

הוּא : ²¹ כִּי־בוֹ יִשְׁמַח לִבֵּנוּ כִּי

בְּשֵׁם קִדְשׁוֹ בָטַחְנוּ : ²² יְהוָה־

חַסְדֵּיךָ יְהוָה עָלֵינוּ כַּאֲשֶׁר יִתְּלָנוּ לְךָ :

References

<p>Psalm 33:1 ^aPs 32:11; Phil 3:1; 4:4 ^bPs 92:1; 147:1</p> <p>Psalm 33:2 ^aPs 71:22; 147:7 ^bPs 144:9</p> <p>Psalm 33:3 ^aPs 40:3; 96:1; 98:1; 144:9; Is 42:10; Rev 5:9 ^bPs 98:4</p> <p>Psalm 33:4 ^aPs 19:8 ^bPs 119:90</p> <p>Psalm 33:5 ^aPs 11:7; 37:28 ^bPs 119:64</p> <p>Psalm 33:6 ^aGen 1:6; Ps 148:5; Heb 11:3 ^bPs 104:30 ^cGen 2:1</p> <p>Psalm 33:7 ¹Some versions read <i>in a water skin</i>; i.e. container ^aEx 15:8; Josh 3:16; Ps 78:13</p> <p>Psalm 33:8 ^aPs 67:7 ^bPs 96:9</p> <p>Psalm 33:9 ¹Or <i>stood forth</i> ^aGen 1:3; Ps 148:5</p>	<p>Psalm 33:10 ^aPs 2:1-3; Is 8:10; 19:3</p> <p>Psalm 33:11 ^aJob 23:12; Prov 19:21 ^bPs 40:5; 92:5; 139:17; Is 55:8</p> <p>Psalm 33:12 ^aPs 144:15 ^bEx 19:5; Deut 7:6; Ps 28:9</p> <p>Psalm 33:13 ^aJob 28:24; Ps 14:2 ^bPs 11:4</p> <p>Psalm 33:14 ^a1 Kin 8:39, 43; Ps 102:19</p> <p>Psalm 33:15 ¹Or <i>their heart together</i> ^aJob 10:8; Ps 119:73 ^b2 Chr 16:9; Job 34:21; Jer 32:19</p> <p>Psalm 33:16 ^aPs 44:6; 60:11</p> <p>Psalm 33:17 ^aPs 20:7; 147:10; Prov 21:31</p> <p>Psalm 33:18 ¹Or <i>wait</i> ^aJob 36:7; Ps 32:8; 34:15; 1 Pet 3:12 ^bPs 32:10; 147:11</p> <p>Psalm 33:19 ^aPs 56:13; Acts 12:11 ^bJob 5:20; Ps 37:19</p>
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Psalm 33:20

^aPs 62:1; 130:6; Is 8:17

^bPs 115:9

Psalm 33:21

^aPs 13:5; 28:7; Zech 10:7; John 16:22

Psalm 33:22

¹Or *waited for*

Targum

Psa. 33:1 Give praise, O righteous, in the presence of the LORD; praise is seemly for the upright. ² Give thanks in the presence of the LORD with the lyre; with the harp of ten strings give him praise. ³ Give praise in the presence of the LORD with a new song; praise well with a shout. ⁴ For the word of the LORD is right, and all his deeds are reliable. ⁵ He loves righteousness and justice; the goodness of the LORD fills the Earth. ⁶ By the word of the LORD were the heavens made; and by the breath of his mouth, all their armies. ⁷ Who gathers as in a bottle the waters of the sea; he puts them in the treasuries of the deeps. ⁸ In the presence of the LORD all who dwell on the Earth will be afraid; all the inhabitants of the world will tremble because of him. ⁹ Because he says it, and it is; he commanded, and it took place. ¹⁰ The LORD shattered the counsel of the Gentiles, frustrated the plans of the nations. ¹¹ The counsel of the LORD stands forever, the thoughts of his heart for all generations. ¹² Happy is the man whose god is the LORD, the people that he chose for his inheritance. ¹³ From heaven the LORD looked, he saw all the sons of men. ¹⁴ From the residence of his dwelling he looked out at all the inhabitants of the Earth. ¹⁵ Who created them, forming their heart together, and discerning all their deeds. ¹⁶ The king is not redeemed by the abundance of his forces; the warrior is not saved by the abundance of his strength. ¹⁷ The horse is deceitful for redemption; and by the abundance of its strength one is not saved. ¹⁸ Behold, the eye of the LORD sees those who fear him, those who hope for his kindness. ¹⁹ To save their soul from death, and to keep them alive in famine. ²⁰ Our soul looks for the redemption of the LORD; he is our help and shield. ²¹ For our heart will rejoice in his word, because in his holy name we have placed our trust. ²² May your goodness be upon us, O LORD, as we have put our hopes in you.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses are in bold.

Verse 1

The Sage Malbim believed that this Psalm says that the LORD controls the world in two different ways. The first way is through the Laws of Nature, which are pre-ordained and unchanging. The second way is through *hashgachab*. This word means the personal supervision and intervention of the LORD. How the LORD participates in the affairs of humans depends on human deeds for better or for worse.

The Laws of Nature served to conceal the LORD's supervision. All people who genuinely seek to understand this revelation will be elevated. The wicked will become good, and the goodwill will become better.

O righteous people exult the LORD; it is appropriate for the upright to sing praises so that the LORD may reveal His might.

Verse 2

Human speech is inadequate alone to praise the LORD; therefore, the sound of the harp and lyre is necessary.

Render thanks to the LORD with the harp and sing praises to Him with the psaltery.

Verse 3

שִׁירָה לַיהוָה (sheroo-lo) – means “sing to.” The primary usage of this phrase is to denote “singing praises.” The psalmist tells us to sing praises to the invisible hand of the LORD, which is a part of all human history. The difference between verses one and two is in this verse is that the psalmist tells us to sing a new song.

Sing Him a new song, express it intones as it is seemly, with deep inner emotion.

Verse 4

This verse is the theme of the hymn proclaiming the praise of the LORD so that man might come to know and understand Him.

For the word of the LORD is for the upright, and His work is done in faithfulness.

Verse five

The Earth is full of the life-giving love of the LORD. He showers us with blessings. His merciful love fills the Earth. He loves justice as well as righteousness. The LORD requires humanity to be just and loyal to the LORD.

Chesed fills the world with lovingkindness of the LORD, for the LORD loves righteousness and justice.

Verse six

The Heavens were made so that humanity might reach that moral goal of Divine sovereignty which is indicated by the tetragrammaton name of the LORD.

By the word of the LORD, the Heavens were created, and all the hosts were created by His word.

Verse Seven

כִּנְסָה כְּאֵיבָה (konas kanaid) – means “gathers heap.” This construction is used in the Torah to refer to the parting of the Sea of Reeds (Red Sea). This miracle of the LORD occurred outside of the framework of the “laws of nature.” These occasional miracles help humans understand that even the natural and everyday order of things is the work of the LORD. This Psalm calls attention to the parting of the Sea of Reeds as the most significant of all the acts that demonstrated the LORD’s rule and supremacy.

He who gathers the sea's waters like a wall also stores up floods in treasure chambers.

Verse 8

Every human living on the Earth should know that the very ground they are standing on is because the LORD desired to create it.

Therefore, let all the Earth show the LORD reverence; let all the world inhabitants stand back in awe of Him.

Verse 9

The LORD speaks His commandments, and they are fulfilled.

For He spoke, and it was; He also commanded, and it stood still.

Verse 10

מַחְשְׁבוֹת עַמִּים (mach'sheevot ameem) – means “peoples’ plans.” These plans are the thoughts that motivate the acts of humans against one another in their domestic relationships.

The LORD has brought to naught the counsel of the people.

Verse 11

The plans that nations have cherished throughout history, the quest for power, face opposition by the plans of the LORD, which is to establish the kingdom of peace under the supreme sovereignty of love and righteousness.

The counsel of the LORD stands for the people; the thought of His heart shall be the heritage of all generations.

Verse 12

Any nation of the world who believes in the LORD will be blessed.

Blessed is the nation whose God is the LORD, for they will receive His inheritance.

Verse 13

The LORD looked down from Heaven one day and beheld all the sons of man.

Verse 14

This verse is a parallel verse to verse 13.

The LORD looked out on the inhabitants of the Earth from his dwelling place.

Verse 15

The LORD looks upon humans and measures the worth of their deeds by the criteria He established for their creation. The LORD intended for humans to live together and to support each other.

He who fashions their hearts for one another; Who considers all their doing

Verse 16 & 17

The LORD saw the unfettered reign of selfish violence and tyranny as a supreme human goal. Gevurah will judge kings and heroes.

A king is not saved by a mighty army, nor is a hero delivered by his strength.

A horse is a vain hope for victory, nor can it escape by its great strength.

Verse 18

The LORD watches human actions to see if these actions are guided solely by His commandments. Those who call upon Chesed will receive the love of the LORD.

Behold the eye of the LORD is toward all who revere Him, and they hope for Chesed to shine upon them.

Verse 19

Parts of this Psalm relate to the time of Israel's departure from Egypt. In this verse, the psalmist talks about the LORD's deliverance from physical and national annihilation in Egypt. The LORD fed His people with manna from Heaven.

To deliver their souls from death and to keep them alive in famine.

Verse 20

It was our soul that waited for the LORD; He is still our help and our shield.

Verse 21

We should place our trust and faith in the LORD.

For it is only in the LORD that our heart rejoices because we have put our trust in His Holy name.

Verse 22

May Chesed be upon us LORD, we have waited for you.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

O righteous people exult the LORD; it is appropriate for the upright to sing praises so that the LORD may reveal His might.

Render thanks to the LORD with the harp and sing praises to Him with the psaltery.

Sing Him a new song, express it intones as it is seemly, with deep inner emotion.

For the word of the LORD is for the upright, and His work is done in faithfulness.

Chesed fills the world with lovingkindness of the LORD, for the LORD loves righteousness and justice.

By the word of the LORD, the Heavens were created, and all the hosts were created by His word.

He who gathers the sea's waters like a wall also stores up floods in treasure chambers.

Therefore, let all the Earth show the LORD reverence; let all the world inhabitants stand back in awe of Him.

For He spoke, and it was; He also commanded, and it stood still.

The LORD has brought to naught the counsel of the people.

The counsel of the LORD stands for the people; the thought of His heart shall be the heritage of all generations.

Blessed is the nation whose God is the LORD, for they will receive His inheritance.

The LORD looked down from Heaven one day and beheld all the sons of man.

The LORD looked out on the inhabitants of the Earth from his dwelling place.

He who fashions their hearts for one another; Who considers all their doing

A king is not saved by a mighty army, nor is a hero delivered by his strength.

A horse is a vain hope for victory, nor can it escape by its great strength.

Behold the eye of the LORD is toward all who revere Him, and they hope for
Chesed to shine upon them.

To deliver their souls from death and to keep them alive in famine.

It was our soul that waited for the LORD; He is still our help and our shield.

For it is only in the LORD that our heart rejoices because we have put our trust
in His Holy name.

May Chesed be upon us LORD, we have waited for you.

Appendix

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Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

